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eScience center

Technology Forecast

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Executive summary

The eScience Center's Technology Forecast highlights transformative trends in artificial intelligence (AI), computing, data processing and data analytics.

Key Points:

AI-powered innovations: AI advancements in natural language processing (NLP) and computer vision promise to revolutionize data analytics, with efficiency gains and cost reductions expected.

Computing challenges: addressing limitations through hardware specialization and exotic architectures like quantum computing poses programming challenges, potentially leading to a shortage of experts.

Cloud solutions: cloud-based access to high-performance computing (HPC) hardware is increasing, emphasizing the need for portable libraries to prevent vendor lock-in.

Data explosion and edge computing: improved sensors and Internet of things (IoT) devices result in a data explosion, leading to efforts to process data closer to sources for cost reduction and enhanced privacy.

FAIR principles: adherence to FAIR data principles is crucial for a highly distributed infrastructure, promoting findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability.

Data analytics: to meet challenges in extracting value from massive amounts of unstructured data, recent developments focus on techniques like dimensionality reduction and incremental learning.

Augmented analytics and edge insights: augmented analytics targets accessibility for non-experts, while edge analytics ensures real-time insights closer to data sources.

This forecast has profited from the feedback of technology experts covering a wide range of expertise. The feedback was gathered through an anonymous survey between 2022 and 2023. We are grateful to the time and dedication of the community, without whom this forecast would not be possible.

1. Artificial intelligence (AI)

The so-called ‘democratization of AI’ will be a key topic in the coming years. As the significance of AI continues to grow, many parts of the AI value chain will become more easily accessible. These include data generation, visualization, storage, ingestion, algorithms, model development and usage.

AI-powered NLP as a tool for data collection, processing and analytics will be broadly adopted. Powered by advanced NLP language prediction models, we expect to see a robust growth in question answering as well as natural language generation.

Likewise, AI-powered Computer Vision (CV) will automate, accelerate, and enhance research across numerous disciplines. Early adopters of AI-powered CV anticipate lower costs and greater efficiency and predict that CV will be a prerequisite for innovation.

AI for science

Application-agnostic algorithms for generic image or NLP typically cannot be applied directly to scientific data. The impact of AI on science centres on three key machine learning (ML) technologies for improving AI with scientific knowledge:

- Scientific ML (SciML) uses tools from both ML and scientific computing to develop new methods for scalable, domain-aware, and interpretable learning and data analysis.
- Adaptive ML refers to ML algorithms that can cope with concept drift, where training and real data distributions shift over time.
- Lifelong Machine Learning (LLML) is an advanced ML paradigm for continuous learning, where knowledge learned in the past accumulates to help future learning.

“AI will transform science – now researchers must tame it.”

Nature editorial, September 2023

Responsible AI

The rapid growth of AI will come with a renewed focus on responsibility. The generic term responsible AI refers to designing, developing and deploying AI with good intentions. More specifically, we will see a rise in:

- Explainable AI (XAI): methods that facilitate human understanding of the results produced by an AI. Extracting new scientific insights from scientific data requires human-interpretable AI models or outputs. XAI stands in contrast to the “black box” in ML, where even their designers cannot explain why the AI arrived at a specific decision.
- Ethical AI: AI that adheres to well-defined ethical guidelines regarding fundamental values, including individual rights, privacy, non-discrimination and non-manipulation. Ethical AI has an immediate bearing on almost any scientific research conducted with the help of AI.

“The superpowers of AI come with great responsibility.”

Atonia Neri, CEO, Hewlett-Packard Enterprise, July 2023

Reuse of AI

FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The FAIR principles apply to all digital objects, not only data but software, workflows and ML models. To stimulate faster, generalizable, and reproducible research, defining FAIR for ML models and facilitate the sharing of these models is a desideratum for the near future.

Some FAIR for ML initiatives already combines data and research software repositories, and function as platforms for finding, comparing, and using ML models. Such open science technologies will boost AI reusability in research.

“FAIR AI models and data may be coupled with modern scientific data infrastructure and innovative computing to automate and accelerate discovery.”

Huerta, Lead Translational AI, Argonne National Laboratory, Scientific Data, February 2022

Self-supervision

Self-supervised learning (or self-supervision) is a form of autonomous supervised learning. Unlike supervised learning, this technique does not require humans to label data: it handles the labelling task by itself. Currently self-supervision is mostly used in computer vision and NLP tasks, for instance in employing Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) models for image colourisation or language translation.

Self-supervision will impact research across numerous disciplines. In healthcare, for example, the technique can be used in robotic surgeries and estimating the dense depth in monocular endoscopy. Auto-encoders and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are also used for anomaly detection, which is highly relevant in observational research and has already been combined with quantum computing.

“Self-supervised learning is the key to human-level intelligence.”

Yann Lecunn and Yashua Bengio, Turing award winners 2018

Federated learning

In centralized ML techniques, local datasets are uploaded to one server, while in classical decentralized approaches local data samples are assumed to be identically distributed.

The future will see the rise of federated learning or collaborative learning: an ML technique that trains an algorithm across multiple decentralized devices or servers holding local data samples, without exchanging them. Federated learning in medicine already facilitates multi-institutional collaborations without sharing patient data.

“Advancements in AI technologies like federated learning and swarm learning are paving the way for novel AI applications in heavily regulated – and privacy forward – industries like healthcare.”

Adam Green, MIT Technology Review, autumn 2022

2. Computing

Improvements in the compute performance of modern hardware are limited by the ‘end of Moore’s law’ and the ‘von Neumann bottleneck.’ These limitations are being addressed through increased hardware specialization for further performance gains. This has resulted in heterogeneous systems containing a range of accelerators on which many large exa-scale machines now appearing in computational facilities rely. Even more exotic architectures, such as in-storage computing, optical computing or quantum computing are on the horizon.

These developments come at a cost. Such systems are harder to program, as traditional programming models and languages are often a poor fit for these architectures. Consequently, use of specialized languages and in-depth knowledge of the hardware is often required to use these systems efficiently. It is likely that in the near future, such experts will be in short supply. At the same time, traditional computing approaches are becoming more accessible through cloud-based solutions for a large group of researchers with (relatively) undemanding applications. Commercial cloud vendors offer pay-per-hour access to HPC hardware (such as graphics processing unit (GPU) machines or compute clusters). Since different vendors offer their own application programming interface (APIs), it is important to use portable libraries to prevent vendor lock-in.

Digital twins

Poster from the annual [eScience Center – Lorentz Competition](#) in 2023

Digital twins form a bridge between research and real-world applications, where engineers, farmers, doctors, planners and others need to take decisions. In the past, such decisions were often based on experience. With digital twins, decisions can be based on models and data, resulting in reproducible, explainable, and shareable results. As virtual representations of real-world objects or systems, digital twins are typically based on several coupled models, sometimes supported by machine learning, and refined with real-time data. They will enable new insights and allow researchers and policy makers to run what-if scenarios, supporting decision making.

“If we can create a digital representation of the world and we can add some funky analysis then it gives us digital superpowers.”

James Dean, Co-founder of SenSat, Financial Times Opinion Technology Sector, January 2022

Heterogeneity++

General purpose computing architectures have reached their limits. Specialized architectures are needed to deliver the necessary performance within an acceptable power budget. While GPUs have been at the forefront for more than a decade, the accelerator landscape (GPU, tensor processing unit (TPU), data processing unit (DPU), field-programmable gate arrays (FPGA), neural processors), like the central processing unit (CPU) landscape (Intel, advance micro devices (AMD), Power, advanced reduced instruction set computer (RISC) machine (ARM), RISC-V), is diversifying rapidly.

The current 'Cambrian explosion of architectures' has been brought on by the circumstance that there is no 'one-size-fits-all' solution for all workloads. It is therefore likely that future HPC architectures will need to offer a wide range of accelerators in every node (or even integrate them into the processor die or package). For research using HPC, up-to-date knowledge of the full range of accelerators will be required to use architectures efficiently. Different parts of an application may need to be mapped to different accelerators, each with different optimizations.

“A challenge of heterogeneity is how to build large systems comprised of massive numbers of these already heterogeneous systems.”

Bob Colwell, former Intel Chip Architect and DARPA MTO Director

HPC cloud

HPC is the next step for cloud vendors offering storage and data analytics. Azure, Amazon, Google and others already offer a range of solutions. Outsourcing the hassle of maintaining, running and upgrading HPC to commercial entities makes increasingly more sense. We expect cloud-based access to HPC infrastructures to become more accessible to researchers. To avoid the vendor lock-in, smart choices will have to be made.

“Cloud is about how you do computing, not where you do computing.”
Paul Maritz, VMware CEO

Energy-aware computing

HPC machines and applications are restricted by their energy budgets, typically 20 megawatt (MW). The required amount of power and cooling determines the maximum size of the supercomputer. Similarly, but at the smallest scales, power is a major concern for mobile devices, smart sensors and edge computing.

The biggest culprit is moving around data. Simply moving 32 bits of data from memory to CPU takes about 100 times more energy than performing a computation on that data. When optimizing code to improve performance and/or scalability, the focus is often on minimizing wall clock time, while energy efficiency is forgotten. We expect a strong emphasis on optimizing data locality to reduce energy consumption.

“Energy efficiency (as opposed to area or switching speeds) is becoming the limiting factor in computing performance.”

Thomas F. Wenisch Alper Buyuktosunoglu, IBM T.J. Watson Research Center, 2012

Scalable ML

In practice, scalable ML is about finding more efficient algorithms, or approximations to the original algorithm, that can be computed much more efficiently. Scalable ML is able to meet specific domain challenges in scientific ML, such as a large volume of mixed data as well as training scalability. We expect efforts in this field to grow substantially.

Embedded AI is a version of scalable ML: the application of ML and deep learning in software at the device level. Embedded AI will find its application in every technical and social domain, including smart robots, smart sensing and health.

“Creating scalable AI systems requires disciplined engineering approach to guide their development, deployment, and maintenance.”

National AI Engineering Initiative, Carnegie Mellon University, 2021

Quantum computing

Quantum computers utilize quantum-mechanical phenomena such as superposition and entanglement to perform computations. Unlike classical bits, which can only possess either 0 or 1 as states, qubits can represent linear combinations of both values. This allows a large state space to be stored in a relatively small number of qubits. Quantum computers are potentially ground-breaking for certain classes of computational problems, such as prime factorization and simulating quantum systems, which cannot be solved efficiently using classical computing.

The investments needed to create usable quantum computers are huge, as the hardware is complex and needs to run at close to zero Kelvin temperatures. Currently large investments are made at the commercial and national levels, and new programming languages, software development kits (SDKs) and demo systems are being created. We expect the interest in quantum computing to continue in the foreseeable future.

“Nature is not classical, dammit, and if you want to make a simulation of nature, you'd better make it quantum mechanical.”

Richard Feynman, May 1981

High-level-languages and domain specific languages

```
        'role_id' => $role_details['id'],
        'resource_id' => $resource_details['id'],
    );
    if ( $this->rule_exists( $resource_details['id'], $role_details['id'], $details ) ) {
        if ( $access == false ) {
            // Remove the rule as there is currently no need for it
            $details['access'] = !$access;
            $this->_sql->delete( 'acl_rules', $details );
        } else {
            // Update the rule with the new access value
            $this->_sql->update( 'acl_rules', array( 'access' => $access ) );
        }
    }
    foreach( $this->rules as $key=>$rule ) {
        if ( $details['role_id'] == $rule['role_id'] && $details['resource_id'] == $rule['resource_id'] ) {
            if ( $access == false ) {
                unset( $this->rules[ $key ] );
            } else {
                $this->rules[ $key ]['access'] = $access;
            }
        }
    }
}
```

Developments in compute have gone hand in hand with work on programming languages. These include new general-purpose languages such as Julia, Rust and Go. Also, due attention is being paid to domain-specific languages (DSLs) that ease programming and improve portability for a specific domain, next to languages designed for new computing paradigms, including quantum computing.

Julia is increasingly becoming a preferred language, as it combines the advantages of both lower-level and higher-level languages. We expect that it will soon be considered a mainstream programming language.

"We want a language that's open source, with a liberal license. We want the speed of C with the dynamism of Ruby. We want a language that's homoiconic, with true macros like Lisp, but with obvious, familiar mathematical notation like Matlab."

Jess Bezanon, Stefan Karpinski, Viral B. Shah, Alan Edleman, Julia developers, February 2012

3. Data processing

Improved and smarter sensors and scientific instrumentation (e.g. cameras, depth sensors, remote sensing, telescopes and microscopes), in combination with an explosive growth of IoT devices in diverse forms, has led to a data explosion. A current challenge is to process this data while avoiding enormous amounts of data traffic. We expect much future effort will be spent on bringing computing power closer to sensors and other devices at the edge of a network. This will significantly reduce the cost of data movement, lower local response times and improve data privacy.

The highly distributed infrastructure needed for this will have a major impact on the way raw data is collected and prepared for processing. The FAIR data principles, data annotation and data semantics will be key elements in such an approach. There is an urgent need to develop reliable and scalable distributed data analytics tools, as well as a software infrastructure that can orchestrate and communicate with various systems to make them interoperable, while virtualizing important components of IT (information technology) infrastructure, including storage, networking, and compute.

Smart & autonomous sensors and IoT resources

With most data being generated at the edge, IoT systems will not be able to process data within the needed timeframe. It is therefore crucial to process data as close as possible to the devices, aggregating it in scalable and efficient ways, for example by using AI at the edge. Smart and autonomous sensors will minimize the need for a global decision point in large-scale infrastructures.

“The missing piece of the IoT puzzle is the software. This is now solvable with AI. The enabling technology of IoT is AI.”

Jensen Huang, Co-founder, President and CEO of Nvidia Corporation, October 2020

Data preparation for curation for AI

Robust and predictive AI models depend on the quality of the input data, both for analytical and training purposes. However, manual curation of data is inefficient and not scalable. To speed up and improve the data curation lifecycle, we expect that considerable effort will be devoted to automated and smart data preparation and curation. This includes harmonization, regrinding and resampling, data enrichment, and information on data provenance and data lineage.

“No data is clean, but most is useful.”

Dean Abbott, Co-founder and Chief Scientist at SMarterHQ

Event stream processing

Event stream processing is a technology that processes single data points rather than a whole data set. It enables applications that respond to data on the fly. Exhibiting properties such as self-management, self-healing and self-configuration, complex smart sensor systems will increasingly integrate data processing and analytics. We expect a steady increase in the adoption of event-driven architectures and the concomitant asynchronous programming techniques.

“A new way of storing and exchanging data without losing out on our ability to created loosely coupled autonomous architectures.”

Ben Stopford, Engineer and Architecture on the Apache Kafka core, 2018

Semantic technology and linked data

Semantic technologies and linked data will address the scalability of reasoning, the use of lightweight ontologies, and the maintenance of ontologies. An important current trend is the large-scale semantic integration of linked data. This includes advanced dataset discovery and selection, reasoning about data quality and veracity, measurements and service provision on a global scale, and evaluation of collections and reproducible results. On the longer term, the combination of semantics and compute power will enable reasoning, semantic data mining, enrichment with data quality and data provenance, and automated annotation, all at the scale of the world-wide web.

“Breaking the four rules of linked data does not destroy anything but misses an opportunity to make data interconnected. This in turn limits the ways it can later be reused in unexpected ways.”

Tim Berners-Lee, Linked Data, July 2006

Distributed management of geospatial data

Geospatial data typically involves large sets of spatial data gleaned from many diverse sources in varying formats. It is available in large quantities, due in part to technologies such as Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR), Radio Detection and Ranging (RADAR), unmanned aerial systems (UAS), thermal imagery, hyperspectral satellite data and aerial photography.

Such remote sensing data has specific characteristics and due to the large number of data providers, its storage will necessarily be distributed. In the future we will see the design of new spatial data models to accommodate distributed storage and improve the flexibility and scalability of geospatial big data processing.

“Many evidences have witnessed that a significant portion of big data is, in fact, geospatial big data. We can innovate our daily life and business by exploiting the power of location embedded in geospatial big data.”

Jae-Gil Lee, Geospatial big data: challenges and opportunities, June 2015

Adoption of FAIR principles

Making data reusable and increasing trust in data are two important trends. The FAIR principles provide information that allows potential (re)users to judge the accuracy, reliability and quality of the data, thus supporting the ability of machines to automatically find and (re)use the data. To achieve this goal not only the data has to be FAIR. So should the basis in which interoperability and reuse are grounded, namely schemas for both the data and the metadata structure, as well as ontologies and vocabularies.

“Good research data management is not a goal in itself, but rather the key conduit leading to knowledge discovery and innovation, and to subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse.”

Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020

4. Data analytics

With the explosion of digital data in society, data analytics is becoming an essential tool for research. Data analytics transcends conventional data processing. It adds substantial value to every stage of the data lifecycle, from generating actionable insights and optimizing resource utilization to enhancing user experiences and fostering innovation. The challenge facing data analytics lies in developing and designing mining algorithms capable of extracting value from vast, unstructured, heterogeneous, high-dimensional and noisy amounts of raw data.

Recent achievements in distributed computing and big data processing platforms have furthered the development of fundamental techniques for large-scale data processing, such as dimensionality reduction, data condensation, density-based approaches, and incremental learning, among others. Augmented analytics, which aims to make emerging technologies accessible to non-experts, while edge analytics ensures real-time insights closer to the data source. As scientific disciplines become increasingly data-intensive, the application of analytics techniques accelerates the pace of discovery, fosters interdisciplinary collaboration and illuminates innovative solutions.

Dimensionality reduction

Data is not just being generated at massive scale, but it is also becoming highly dimensional. The so-called ‘curse of dimensionality’ makes dimension reduction techniques even more important. Dimension reduction flattens the data for consumption with as little distortion as possible. Over the last two decades several methods (linear and non-linear) have been developed and used successfully in several application domains. Dimension reduction is finally becoming scalable due to better GPUs and TPUs in addition to faster approximation methods. It will thus become feasible to create visualizations of very large datasets.

“The curse of dimensionality has turned out to be a misnomer, as neural networks are trainable only due to the counterintuitive behavior of billion-dimensional spaces. Maybe time to be renamed to ‘gift of dimensionality’.”

Greg Brockman President & Co-founder @OpenAI, September 2023

Privacy-preserving analytics

Privacy preserving analytics involves protecting data when it is at rest or in motion, and during analytics. Much recent work on privacy has been spurred on by the introduction of the GDPR in 2018. Several trends can be distinguished in current approaches to privacy-preserving analytics. One approach involves sharing data through trusted (third) parties, based on techniques such as remote access, compute to data, and trusted third party computation. Another is obfuscating sensitive data, through anonymization, differential privacy, or homomorphic encryption (where computations are performed on the encrypted data itself). A third trend is secure multiparty computation, centred on distributed processing and encrypted channels.

“Privacy-preserving data share and analytics technologies help advance the well-being and prosperity of individuals and society and promote science and innovation in manner that affirms democratic values.”

National strategy to advance privacy-preserving data sharing and analytics,
Executive Office of the President of the USA, March 2023

Interactive visualization

Interactive visualization faces several challenges: efficiency issues due to scale, the complexity of the data being visualized and the need for user experience to be as easy and natural as possible. A major game-changer in interactive visualization is the use of AI techniques to process massive datasets and provide instant analysis of the data, or even generate images from scratch using only collections of data. We expect substantial effort to be invested in achieving near real-time image generation. Recent progress in augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) is expected to change the way we visualize and interact with data. In particular the concept of the metaverse, a platform combining social media with AR and VR, may make these technologies commonplace, with certain impact on research and education.

“Interactive visualization is qualitatively different from generating images or sequences of images in batch mode; it provides a smooth, user-in-the-loop visualization process. This interactive process helps to deal with the challenging problem of finding the interesting aspects of some data through manipulations of a large space of visualization parameters.”

Jonathan D. Cohen, Johns Hopkins University, April 2023

Storytelling

The significance of adopting storytelling techniques to make sense of the wealth of data available in the world today cannot be overstated. The traditional approach of displaying raw data through dashboards and spreadsheets often falls short when engaging non-technical data users. Data storytelling is emerging as a powerful methodology to create a compelling narrative that can communicate complex patterns in the data to a general audience. At its core, data story telling combines three essential aspects: data, narrative and visualization. The combination of these elements transforms data into a meaningful and accessible form, allowing individuals to not only comprehend the information but also connect with it on a deeper level. Data storytelling will become more challenging as the source (data) becomes larger, less complete and more biased.

“The brain’s preference for stories over pure data stems from the fact that it takes in so much information every day and needs to determine what’s important to process and remember and what we can discarded.”

The Psychological Power of Storytelling, Harvard Business School

Web development

A new wave of web technologies will unlock capabilities vital to researchers advocating accessible and impactful science. While in the past decade key technologies like JavaScript and Ajax were central, a range of emerging technologies will further expand the role of web browsers in scientific computing.

One such technology, Web Assembly, is revolutionizing how code written in languages like C, Python and Rust operates within web browsers. It delivers near-native performance, eliminating the need for local installations and ensuring that complex research tools function seamlessly across different platforms.

WebGPU has emerged as a powerful asset for web applications, providing high-quality graphics and robust data processing capabilities. Researchers can now transform extensive datasets into interactive visualizations, not only enhancing the depth of their analyses but also making the information more engaging for users. WebXR complements this advancement by bringing high-quality graphics and computational capabilities to virtual and augmented reality environments, enhancing scientific research.

“The good news is that there are just as many opportunities for innovation in the back end as there are in the front end.”

Gerry Katz, Vice Chairman Emeritus, Applied Marketing Science, Inc.

Colophon

This forecast has profited from the feedback of technology experts covering a wide range of expertise. The feedback was gathered through an anonymous survey between 2022 and 2023. We are grateful to the time and dedication of the community, without whom this forecast would not be possible.

This report was written by Adam Belloum, Willem van Hage, Jason Maassen, Rob van Nieuwpoort and Elena Rangelova.

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netherlands
eScience center

Science Park 402 (Matrix THREE)
1098 XH Amsterdam
+31 (0)20 460 4770

info@esciencecenter.nl
www.esciencecenter.nl

